

Talent Management in Competency and E-Assessment to Improve Performance and Employee's Commitment after Pandemic

Sudarsih

Faculty of Economics and Business
University of Jember (UNEJ)

Supriyadi

Jember State Polytechnic

Abstract:-

Purpose: to determine the influence of talent management, namely competence and E-Assessment on the performance and commitment of the employees of the University of Jember, especially the New Normal period after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Design/methodology/approach: This research design is a quantitative research. This research is a type of explanatory research. The research was conducted at the University of Jember

Findings: 1) Competence has a direct effect on the organizational commitment of the employees of the University of Jember; 2) E-Assessment has a direct effect on the organizational commitment of the employees of the University of Jember; 3) competence does not directly affect the performance of Jember University employees; 4) E-Assessment has a significant effect on the performance of Jember University employees; 5) Employee organizational commitment affects the performance of employees at the University of Jember

Keywords:- e-assessment, performance, commitment, competence and talent.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the concepts of managing government organizations to be able to serve the community well is the concept of "good governance" which shows performance in efforts to improve and improve government management processes so that service performance becomes better. The pattern and style of government must immediately be addressed and developed with the concept of "good governance" with efforts to improve human resources who are more professional and well behaved in serving the community by developing talent management. Talent management is getting more and more attention from both practitioners and academics (Sonnenberg *et al.*, 2014). Talent management has become the main agenda of most organizations because of the belief in the importance of talent in achieving organizational excellence (Iles *et al.*, 2010).

Talent management is linked to organizational performance. Organizational performance although it is well recognized that the total number of individuals leads to organizational performance. Talent management is structured to provide guidance for organizations in managing and developing talent so that the talents (talents

of employees are expected to be optimized to carry out tasks as strategic objectives in human resource investment. Management and talent development carried out by companies often cannot meet the expectations of the organization's strategic goals, resulting in problems that cause stress for employees and also decrease organizational performance and development cost efficiency. The talent management strategy is expected to be able to consistently combine all employees with the expression of performance expected by the organization, so that managers are responsible for conducting the appraisal process, rewarding, and ensuring that employees are responsible for achieving specific business goals, creating innovation and striving for sustainable change. This is supported by several previous studies, the following is a research gap on talent management related to organizational performance.

Talent management is continuously developed by the University of Jember in human resource management policies. Talent management aims to attract qualified Human Resources (HR) to occupy structural or functional positions. This talent management system pays attention to three main components, namely, qualifications, competence and performance, which will become the standard for organizations in mapping employees into talent management schemes such as the E-Assessment that was initiated during the pandemic. This is an effort to improve the ability of Jember University employees in serving the community, especially during the New Normal period after the COVID-19 pandemic.

Talent management and human resource quality as measured in relation to the human resource management strategy. Singh and Rao (2017) who examined the effect of implementing human resource management on knowledge management and its impact on employee performance, Glaister *et al.* (2017) which examines the effect of implementing human resource management on talent management and company performance and Son *et al.* (2018) and Mwanzi *et al.* (2017) which examines the influence of talent management on organizational performance. Andi *et al.* (2021), Nurzaman (2020) and Babyr *et al.* (2020) explained that organizational commitment has a significant effect on employee performance.

Talent management consists of competency and task assessment in this case E-Assessment as one of the new programs of the University of Jember in determining employee performance in providing services during the COVID-19 pandemic. Garaika (2020) found that the

significant positive effect of competence on performance. Hanum (2020) found that competence and knowledge management affect positively and significantly on performance. Mutiara *et al.*, (2019) found that talent management has a significant effect on performance. In addition, it was also explained that talent management which consists of competence and e-assessment can increase organizational commitment. Anwar and Asma (2021) found that competence, motivation and organizational commitment had a significant positive effect on employee performance, both partially and simultaneously. Besides that, organizational commitment variable does not mediate competence and motivation variables on employee performance. Makhfudho and Abadiyah (2019) found that competence has an effect on organizational commitment. Silaban, *et al.* (2021) found that competence has a significant effect on performance through organizational commitment. In addition, the variable that can affect performance and commitment is assessment. M. Alkhateeb (2019) found that assessment had a significant effect on performance. Assessment is carried out to determine the competencies possessed by everyone who works in the company. To carry out this process, HR usually cooperates with a psychology bureau to get the best results.

The years 2020 to 2021 are very extraordinary years, the COVID-19 pandemic makes the challenges of the University of Jember even higher to provide better work results. The University of Jember in an effort to improve services for the quality of education is focused on developing employee behavior. Jember University develops human resources in the context of optimizing services to the community. However, at this time there are still some phenomena about the condition of the University of Jember that need to be a subject of attention and improvement. The phenomenon of the conditions that form the basis for conducting research at the University of Jember, among others, the University of Jember as a service provider of education is still not optimal. This is evidenced by the results of the initial survey using community respondents or agencies served by respondents who acknowledged that there was a significant increase in the quality of services provided by the University of Jember. However, some respondents who receive services still have relatively the same complaints. With the development of human resources at the University of Jember, the aims of study, among others, were to determine the influence of talent management, namely competence and E-Assessment on the performance and commitment of Jember University employees, especially the New Normal period after the COVID-19 pandemic.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Talent management

Yamall (2011) says that talent management includes the selection and development of employees who are considered talented in the company produced by the company whose talents can be developed to become an investment in the company. Talent management is an effort to find, develop, plan and maintain the talent possessed by someone in an organization that is needed to develop the company's business and assets for the company that must be maintained.

Talent management is a dynamic capability by which companies understand, seize, and transform their skills, resources and competencies (Linden and Teece, 2014). According to Ambrosini and Bowman (2009), dynamic capabilities focus on the future and develop the most adequate resource base, the value of which comes from its output. The foundation for implementing human resource management, applied to the entire workforce, mainly consists of ordinary or basic abilities (Fainshmidt *et al.* 2016). Thus, talent management can be seen as a transmission mechanism that allows organizations to continuously change. Fainshmidt *et al.* (2016) show that dynamic capabilities in emerging markets yield superior benefits because they tend to be scarce and can provide added value in volatile economic conditions.

B. Competence

McClelland in Rivai and Sagala (2018) defines competence as a fundamental characteristic possessed by a person that has a direct influence on, or can predict, excellent performance. In other words, competence is what outstanding performers do more often in more situations with better results, than what average performers do. A competency refers to an individual's demonstrated knowledge, skills, or abilities (KSA's) performed to a specific standard.

Competencies are observable, behavioral acts that require a combination of KSA's execute. They are demonstrated in a job context and as such, are influenced by an organization's culture and work environment. In other words, competencies consist of a combination of knowledge, skills and abilities that are necessary in order to perform a major task or function in the work setting (JGN Consulting Denver, USA). Competency comprises knowledge and skills and the consistent application of that knowledge and skills to the standard of performance required in employment (Competency Standards Body Canberra 1994) (Rivai and Sagala, 2018).

Based on the three definitions above, it can be formulated that competence is defined as a person's ability that can be observed which includes knowledge, competence, and attitude in completing a job or task in accordance with the specified performance. According to Rivai and Sagala (2018), there are various approaches to the competency model. One of them is competency-based HRM (competency-based HR management). The point is that the behavior of employees with the best performance is used as a benchmark. This behavior becomes the standard that

drives HR programs to develop more effective work groups. The standards of behavior of employees with the best performance and proven to support the company's strategy are the basis for HR management policies, such as recruitment, selection, reward, performance management, promotion, and development. In this way, it means that strategy and HR management have been linked with corporate strategy and management.

C. E-Assessment

According to Sani (2014), assessment is an effort to collect data which is then processed for policy making of a work program. In work, employees conduct an assessment by collecting facts and employee work documents to make improvements to work planning. Therefore, the process of evaluating the work process and results requires information that varies from each employee or group of employees. Appropriate assessment can provide a reflection of work events experienced by employees. Hasibuan (2018) states that the employee appraisal method is a method or procedure used to assess employees regarding the strengths and weaknesses as well as the potential possessed by the employee concerned, in order to obtain an objective assessment result of the employee being assessed.

One of the work appraisal systems that is often carried out by companies is through E-Assessment, which is an evaluation of behavior using a certain standard based on several online inputs. In obtaining this input, there were various techniques and observations carried out by several trained assessors. The final decision on the assessment is made based on the results of the integration of several assessors on a number of simulations that have been applied to participants. In this integration discussion, the assessor conducts a comprehensive discussion of the participant's behavior and considers how often the behavior appears.

D. Organizational Commitment

Kreitner and Kinicki (2010) say that organizational commitment reflects the extent to which an individual identifies with an organization and is committed to its goals. Organizational commitment reflects a person's level of identification with the organization and implement it to achieve organizational goals. Meanwhile, McDonald and Makin (2011) view that "Organizational commitment as a psychological treaty signed between the person and the organization". This definition shows that organizational commitment is basically a form of psychological agreement between individuals and their organizations. This means that commitment is a bond that exists between an individual and his institution.

According to McShane and Glinow (2010), Organizational commitment is the employee's emotional attachment to identification with and involvement in a particular organization. With this definition, they see that organizational commitment is more about one's emotional involvement in the organization. This shows that

organizational commitment has a tendency for emotions to be expressed in the organization. Meanwhile, Meyer and Allen as quoted by Luthans (2015) identify three indicators of organizational commitment, namely:

- Affective commitment, namely: "involves the employee's emotional attachment to, identification with, is involvement in the organization".
- Rational organizational commitment (continuance commitment), namely: "involves commitment based on the cost that the employee associated with leaving the organization."
- Normative commitment, namely: "involved employee's feeling of obligation to stay with the organization".

Basically, organizational commitment is not limited to leaders who hold functional and structural positions, but to all employees in the organization. Organizational commitment of every employee in the organization can be influenced by organizational characteristics, because employees who have high performance will increasingly develop if they work in an organizational environment that has high performance organizational commitment supported by employee morale, requiring employees to have a strong work organization commitment. high, so that such an environment will affect employees to increase their organizational commitment.

E. Employee performance

According to Pradhan and Jena (2017), performance is a multi-component concept and a fundamental level that can be distinguished based on performance aspects, namely behavioral aspects of expected results. Behavior shows the actions of people who show to complete a job, while the results state about the consequences of individual work behavior. Meanwhile, according to (Hadiyatno, 2012) that performance is the result of work that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities, in an effort to achieve the goals of the organization concerned legally, not violating the law and in accordance with morals or ethics. Anitha (2014) explain employee performance shows the financial or non-financial results of employees that have a direct relationship with organizational performance and success. Armstrong (2009) in (Ngima and Kyongo, 2013) said that the factors that affect the level of individual performance are motivation, ability and opportunity to participate.

Vroom in his expectancy theory states that people need both ability and motivation to work well and that if ability or motivation is zero, then there will be no effective performance. David (2002) in (Sundi, 2013) said that one of the key factors that affect performance is leadership and work culture. Employees with high work motivation and transformational leadership style influence to improve employee performance. Based on the theory, the research model is explained as follows.

Fig. 1: Research Model

III. METHODOLOGY

This research design is a quantitative research. This research is a type of explanatory research. The research was conducted at the University of Jember. The population in this study were 151 non-lecturer employees. The type of data used in this study consists of primary data (original data) is data obtained directly from respondents by means of direct interviews and questionnaires, this data will be analyzed in this study and secondary data is data obtained not from the main source, but from other parties or from documentation/archive data. This data includes data on the number of employees based on age, education, length of service, class and position, data on the distribution of employee placements, data on education and training that have been carried out,

The data will be processed and presented based on the principles of descriptive statistics, while for the purposes of analysis and hypothesis testing an inferential statistical approach is used. The analysis used to test the hypothesis in this study is a structural equation model (Structural Equation Modeling or SEM). SEM can test together (Bohlen, in Ghazali, 2005: 3):

- Structural model of the relationship between independent and dependent constructs
- Model measurement: relationship (loading value) between indicators and constructs (latent variables).

The combination of structural and measurement model testing allows researchers to:

- Testing measurement error as an integral part of SEM
- Perform factor analysis along with hypothesis testing.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on the characteristics of the respondents, it showed that male respondents are 65% while female respondents are only 35%. This shows that the male gender has a greater proportion than female employees who work at the University of Jember. There is a larger proportion of male employees at the University of Jember because work in general and equipment at the University of Jember requires dexterity and energy which is directly related to strong

physique. The education level of the most respondents is bachelor degree (S1), which is as much as 50.99%. While the education level that has the least number of respondents is high school/equivalent as much as 7.95%. This shows that the college graduation factor is needed in accordance with competent human resources in the field of science and in accordance with their expertise. While other levels of education are absorbed according to the needs of the institution. Based on the years of service of employees at the University of Jember who became respondents, most of them ranged between 11-15 years as many as 47 people (31.13%), meaning that employees in general have worked at the University of Jember for a long period of time. This shows that the level of experience and loyalty of employees to the agency is mature enough to carry out their duties. Most of them are between 11-15 years old as many as 47 people (31.13%), meaning that employees in general have worked at the University of Jember for a long period of time. This shows that the level of experience and loyalty of employees to the agency is mature enough to carry out their duties. Most of them are between 11-15 years old as many as 47 people (31.13%), meaning that employees in general have worked at the University of Jember for a long period of time. This shows that the level of experience and loyalty of employees to the agency is mature enough to carry out their duties.

The results of data analysis using SEM showed that the test variables of the first model were grouped into exogenous variables (exogenous variables) and endogenous variables (endogenous variables). Exogenous variables are variables whose values are determined outside the model. Endogenous variables are variables whose values are determined through equations or from the relationship model formed, included in the group of exogenous variables are competence (X1), E-Assesment (X2), and endogenous variables of organizational commitment (Z) and employee performance (Y). SEM models. The results of the initial model construct test are evaluated based on goodness of fit indices. The model criteria and critical values that have data suitability can be seen in Table 1 below.

<i>Goodness of fit Indices</i>	<i>Cut of value</i>	Model Results	Information
<i>Chi Square</i>	Expected small	453,333	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
<i>Significant Probability</i>	0.05	0.000	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
RMSEA	0.08	0.082	<i>Goodness Fit</i>
GFI	0.90	0.791	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
AGFI	0.90	0.745	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
CMIN/DF	3.00	2.006	<i>Goodness Fit</i>
TLI	0.95	0.823	<i>Marginal Fit</i>
CFI	0.95	0.842	<i>Marginal Fit</i>

Table 1: Evaluation of Criteria for Goodness of Fit Indices

Source: Data processed

Based on Table 1, it can be seen that the model is feasible to use by assuming the Parsimony principle meets the criteria because there are already more than one fulfilling so that this model is feasible to use. The evaluation of the model shows that of the eight goodness of fit indices criteria, all of them have met the criteria and are approaching the recommended critical value. Thus, referring to the parsimony principle, the overall model can be said to be in accordance with the data and can be analyzed further.

Based on the empirical model proposed in this study, it is possible to test the proposed hypothesis through path coefficient testing on the structural equation model. After it is known that the model in this analysis is fit, the next analysis is to determine the level of relationship and the

significance or significance of the relationship between the variables in this study. The results of testing with the AMOS program give the results of a structural equation model that shows a relationship between the variables of competence and organizational commitment, E-Assessment with organizational commitment, competence with performance, E-Assessment with performance, and organizational commitment with performance.

After knowing the description of the relationship between the variables of this study, the results of hypothesis testing will then be presented. In this case, the path coefficient values between variables will be presented along with the significance of the hypothesis test results in Table 2 as follows:

Variable	Path Coefficient	CR	Probability	Information
X1→ Y	-0.849	-0.727	0.467	Not significant
X2→ Y	0.481	4,664	0.000	Significant
X1 → Z	0.803	7,682	0.000	Significant
X2 → Z	0.020	5,465	0.004	Significant
Z→ Y	0.930	5,661	0.009	Significant

Table 2: Path Coefficient Value and Hypothesis Testing

Source: Data processed

The first and second hypotheses in this study state that competence and E-Assessment have a significant effect on the performance of Jember University employees. Based on the results of the existing analysis, it turns out that the value of the competency path coefficient on employee performance is -0.849 with a CR value of -0.727. This CR value is smaller than the required critical value of 2. Thus, it can be stated that competence has no significant effect on the performance of Jember University employees. Meanwhile, E-Assessment has a path coefficient value with employee performance of 0.481 with a CR value of 4.664. This CR value is greater than the required CR value of 2. Based on these results, it can be concluded that E-Assessment has a significant effect on employee performance.

The third and fourth hypotheses in this study state that competence and E-Assessment have a significant and positive effect on employee organizational commitment. Based on Table 2, it is known that the path coefficient value between competence and organizational commitment is

0.803 with a CR value of 7.682 more than the required critical value of 2. Meanwhile, the E-Assessment variable on organizational commitment has a path coefficient value of 0.020 with a CR value of 5,465 more. of a critical value of 2 as required. These results support (accept) the third and fourth hypotheses in this study which state that competence and E-Assessment have a significant and positive effect on organizational commitment of employees of the University of Jember.

The fifth hypothesis in this study states that organizational commitment has a significant effect on employee performance at the University of Jember. Based on the results of the existing analysis, it turns out that the path coefficient of organizational commitment to employee performance is 0.930 with a CR value of 5.661. This CR value is greater than the required critical value of 2. It can be concluded that organizational commitment has a significant effect on the performance of Jember University employees. These results support (accept) the fifth hypothesis in this study which states that organizational commitment has a

significant and positive effect on performance. Jember University employees. Based on the existing results, it can be concluded that all the hypotheses were proven except the first hypothesis in the study that was not proven to have a significant effect.

The factor of organizational commitment and employee performance is something important in an agency because many studies show that organizational commitment is related to improving employee performance. Based on previous data analysis, it can be seen that several human resource factors, including competence and E-Assessment, affect organizational commitment and performance. These results are also supported by the results of descriptive analysis of respondents' answers to the variables of competence, E-Assessment, organizational commitment and performance. The results of the study are explained in full as follows:

A. *The Influence of Competency Factors on Employee Performance*

Based on the results of SEM analysis, competence has no significant effect on performance. In this study, it can be seen that the direct influence of competence on the performance of Jember University employees is not significant. This means that the first hypothesis which states that competence has a significant effect on performance is not proven. Based on the results of the respondent's assessment, it is known that the competencies that are perceived well by employees have a significant effect on employee performance. This is because competence is carried out quite well which then increases good performance for employees. But in its implementation good performance is not only supported by competence but also from other abilities that support the completion of the work.

The results of this study are not consistent with Musringudin *et al.* (2017) stated that competence has an effect on performance. competence will be able to positively affect performance. However, in this study, competence is still influenced by the agency's bureaucracy, not yet fully equal to the performance of employees who depend on the performance of individual employees.

B. *The Influence of E-Assessment Factors on Employee Performance*

The results of the analysis show that E-Assessment has a positive and significant effect on employee performance at the University of Jember. It means that the second hypothesis which states that the stronger the E-Assessment, the higher the employee's performance, is accepted as true. This result is supported by the employee's assessment of E-Assessment which generally has a fairly agree and agree rating. It can be interpreted that employees have a fairly good perception of the E-Assessment implemented at the University of Jember.

E-assessment in the assessment of Jember University employees is part of talent management. This raises awareness and provides knowledge to every official and employee. The transformation that also directly manages the presence of HR in the Jember University employees

explained at the beginning of the event that this talent management system pays attention to three main components, namely, qualifications, competencies and performance, which will become the standard for organizations in mapping employees into talent management schemes. The stages in talent management that need to be understood by employees so as to create a harmonious understanding with the ideal conditions for the level of position required by the organization. In principle, this talent management system is a manifestation of the concept of a merit system in the management of the State Civil Apparatus. The talent management system is an effort to find, manage, develop and retain the best employees who are prepared as future leaders to support the organization's vision, mission and strategy going forward.

Therefore, the commitment of every employee and leader becomes a fundamental element in realizing the implementation of talent management at Customs. Internalization activities took place very dynamically and the employee's interest was reflected in the high intensity of discussions and questions and answers. After this internalization, all participants have more understanding and alignment of paradigms in promoting integrity and objectivity in their work and are able to map their potential, competencies, talents and interests so that the organization can have a significant impact. manage, develop and retain the best employees who are prepared as future leaders to support the organization's vision, mission and strategy going forward.

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The results of this study are consistent with the research of Glaister *et al.* (2017), Son *et al.* (2018) and Mwanzi *et al.* (2017) show that E-Assessment affects employee performance. The type of ability, skill and task fulfillment will positively affect performance. The implementation of the influence of E-Assessment on performance at the University of Jember is realized by the achievement of the performance targets of the education staff at the University of Jember having a good category achievement.

C. The Influence of Competency Factors on Employee Organizational Commitment

Based on the value of competence has a significant effect on organizational commitment. In this study, it can be seen that the direct influence of the competency variable on the organizational commitment of the Jember University employees is proven to be significant. This means that the

third hypothesis which states that competence has a significant effect on organizational commitment is proven. Based on the results of the respondent's assessment, it shows that competencies are perceived well by employees so that competence has a significant effect on employee organizational commitment. This is because the competence of the employees of the University of Jember will lead to good organizational commitment for employees. Strong competencies will support agency goals. This result is in accordance with Garaika (2020) and Hanum (2020) who found that competence has an effect on organizational commitment.

D. The Influence of E-Assessment Factors on Employee Organizational Commitment

Based on the value of E-Assessment has a significant effect on organizational commitment. The results of this study show that the direct influence of the E-Assessment variable on the organizational commitment of the employees of the University of Jember is proven to be significant. This means that the second hypothesis which states that E-Assessment has a significant effect on organizational commitment is proven. Based on the results of the respondent's assessment, it shows that the E-Assessment is well perceived by the employees so that the E-Assessment has a significant effect on the employee's organizational commitment. This is because the E-Assessment of employees at the University of Jember will lead to good organizational commitment for employees.

The implementation of the effect of E-Assessment on organizational commitment includes conducting online assessments during the pandemic. The effect of E-Assessment on employee performance is consistent with research conducted by Sindi and Alini (2014) the effect of E-Assessment on employee performance has a positive and significant influence on employee performance.

E. The Effect of Organizational Commitment on Employee Performance

Organizational commitment is considered a behavior in the workplace that corresponds to a personal judgment that exceeds one's basic job requirements. They are often described as behavior that exceeds the request of the task. Research on organizational commitment has been intensively carried out since its introduction almost twenty years ago (Bateman and Organ, 1983). The majority of organizational commitment research has focused on the effect of organizational commitment on individual and organizational performance.

Results research shows organizational commitment has a positive and significant effect on the performance of employees at the University of Jember. This means that the behavior of employees will play a role in the performance of employees at the University of Jember. This is because employees have a high sensitivity to help co-workers who need help, because this behavior is work behavior only related to formal duties by expecting recognition or compensation and contributing to organizational effectiveness.

Commitment to the organization means more than just formal membership, because it includes an attitude of liking the organization and a willingness to strive for a higher level of effort for the benefit of the organization in order to achieve goals. Based on this definition, organizational commitment includes elements of loyalty to the organization, involvement in work, and identification of the values and goals of the organization. In addition, if an organization considers aspects of high organizational commitment for employees, it will have an effect on improving performance.

The results of this study are in accordance with the theory of Mowday, *et al.* (1982), organizational commitment is an individual identifier, and involvement in the organization, consisting of trust, support for goals, organizational values, a strong desire to work hard for the benefit of the organization, and determined to maintain membership in the organization. The organizational commitment of the company's employees is able to grow the performance of the employees themselves. The results of this study are in accordance with Andi *et al.* (2021), Nurzaman (2020) and Babyr *et al.* (2020) explained that organizational commitment has a significant effect on employee performance.

V. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of a study conducted on employees of the University of Jember, it can be concluded as follows. 1) Competence has a direct effect on the organizational commitment of the employees of the University of Jember. The results of this study indicate that competence has a significant effect on employee organizational commitment. The higher the competence, the higher the organizational commitment of the Jember University employees; 2) E-Assessment has a direct effect on the organizational commitment of the employees of the University of Jember. The results of this study indicate that E-Assessment has a significant effect on employee organizational commitment. The higher the E-Assessment, the higher the organizational commitment of the Jember University employees; 3) competence does not directly affect the performance of Jember University employees. The results of this study indicate that intelligence has a significant effect on employee performance. The higher the intelligence, the higher the performance of the employees of the University of Jember; 4) E-Assessment has a significant effect on the performance of Jember University employees. The results of this study indicate that E-Assessment has a significant effect on employee performance, meaning that the higher the employee's E-Assessment will improve the performance of the employees of the University of Jember and 5) Employee organizational commitment affects the performance of the employees of the University of Jember. This is due to an increase in employee organizational commitment causing employee involvement to achieve work results that are expected to be optimal. If the optimal work results are in accordance with the service, the employee's performance will also increase in accordance with the achievements obtained.

Based on the results of the discussion and conclusions of this study, the following are suggested: 1) Improved E-Assessment for leadership employees at the University of Jember. Therefore, the University of Jember must always carry out continuous supervision of employees; 2) Provide promotion to every employee who has high work performance. The University of Jember must conduct an objective performance assessment to the employees of the University of Jember on a regular basis and transparently so that all employees of the University of Jember know about their performance and employees who are entitled to promotions; 3) The human resources department of the University of Jember to place employees according to the psychology of interest, talent, knowledge and skills they have and provide continuous training related to field specialization and 4) For further researchers should measure organizational commitment and performance not only one part but all parts of the employee so that optimal results can be obtained.

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This research can be useful for students and the University of Jember, especially in order to improve the quality of education, especially during the COVID-19 pandemic.

REFERENCES

- [1.] Kang dan Sidhu, (2014) Manajemen Talenta. *Global business review. Vol. 12, N. 3, pp. 456-471.*
- [2.] Sonnenberg et al, (2014). Performance concepts and performance theory. in psychological management of individual performance. John Wiley and Sons, LTD. Chichester: UK
- [3.] Iles, Paul, Xin Chuai and David Preec. 2010. Talent Management And HRM In Multinational Companies In Beijing: Definitions, Differences And Drivers. *Journal of World Business* 45(2):179-189. DOI:10.1016/j.jwb.2009.09.014
- [4.] Singh, P. K., & Rao, M. K. (2017). HR Practices, Learning Culture and Human Capital A Study on Indian Business and Professional Service Sector. *Global Business Review*, 18(3), 1–13.
- [5.] Glaister, A. J., Karacay, G., Demirbag, M., & Tatoglu, E. (2018). HRM and performance – The role of talent management as a transmission mechanism in an emerging market context. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 28(1), 148–166
- [6.] Son et al. (2018). The Impact of Training and Development on Technical Competence in Open Cast Mines of CCL. *International Research Journal of Engineering and Technology*, 4(6), 5702–5714
- [7.] Mwanzi, J., Wamitu, S., & Kiama, M. (2017). Influence of Talent Management on Organizational Growth. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 19(8), 1–36
- [8.] Andi *et al.* (2021), *Employee Engagement Training and Motivation. KHOJ-Journal of Indian Management Research and Practices*. 12 (3), 14-21
- [9.] Anitha. J. (2014), "Determinants of employee engagement and their impact on employee

- performance", *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, Vol. 63 No. 3, pp. 308-323. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-01-2013-0008>
- [10.] Bayir *et al.*(2020)Knowledge Management and Intellectual Capital—A Theoretical Perspective of Human Resource Strategies and Practices. *European Journal of Economics and Business Studies*, 3(2), 148–155
- [11.] Fainshmidt, S., Pezeshkan, A., Frazier, M. L., Nair, A., & Markowski, E. (2016). Dynamic Capabilities And Organizational Performance: A Meta-Analytic Evaluation And Extension. *Journal of Management Studies*, 141(1), 1348–1380.
- [12.] Garaika, 2020. Impact of Training and Competence on Performance Moderated by The Lecturer Career Development Program In Palembang, Indonesia. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBA) Peer Reviewed – International Journal Vol-4, Issue-3, 2020 (IJEBA)*
- [13.] Hadiyatno, Didik, 2012. Pengaruh Kompetensi, Kompensasi, dan Kepuasan Kerja Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Ciomas Adisatwa Balikpapan. Balikpapan: Universitas Balikpapan.
- [14.] Kreitner, Kinicki. 2010. *Organizational Behavior*. New York: McGraw-Hill.
- [15.] Linden, G., & Teece, D. (2014). Managing expert talent. In P. Sparrow, H. Scullion, & ITarique (Eds). *Strategic Talent Management: Contemporary Issues in InternationaContext*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 87–116.
- [16.] Lunthans, Fred. 2015, *Perilaku Organisasi*, Edisi Sepuluh, Penerbit ANDI, Yogyakarta.
- [17.] M. Alkhateeb.2018. TheEffect of Using Performance-based assessment Strategies to Tenth-Grade Students' Achievement and Self-Efficacy in Jordan. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*
- [18.] Makhfudho And Abadiyah (2019). The Effect Of Competence And Organizational Commitment On Employee Performance With Organizational Citizenship Behavior (Ocb) As Intervening Variables In Pt. Mentari Trans Nusantara In Sidoarjo. *Indonesian Journal Of Law And Economics Review* 5
Doi:10.21070/Ijler.2019.V5.353
- [19.] McShane, Steven L., & Von Glinow, Mary Ann. 2010. *Organizational Behavior: Emerging Knowledge and Practice for The Real World*. New York
- [20.] Musringudin, M., Akbar, M., & Karnati, N. 2017. The Effect Of Organizational Justice, Job Satisfaction, And Organizational Commitment On Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Of The Principles. *Indonesian Journal of Educational Review*, 4(2), 155–165.
- [21.] Mutiara, A. N., Hubeis, A. V., & Sukmawati, A. (2019). Talent Management in Improving The Employees Performance of PT PLN (Persero) TJBB APP Cawang. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship (IJBE)*, 5(1), 96. <https://doi.org/10.17358/ijbe.5.1.96>
- [22.] Ngima, W.M. & Kyongo, J. 2013. *Contribution of Motivational Management to Employee Performance. International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 3 (14), 219-239
- [23.] Pradhan, Rabindra Kumar., Jena, Lalatendu Kesari., 2017 Employee Performance at Workplace: Conceptual Model and Empirical Validation, *Jurnal. India*.
- [24.] Rivai, Veithzal & Jauvani Sagala. 2018. *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia. Untuk Perusahaan Dari Teori ke Praktik*. Jakarta: Rajawali Press
- [25.] Sani (2014), Kepemimpinan Transaksional, Transformasional, Servant Leadership Pengaruhnya Terhadap Kinerja Karyawan Pada PT. Sinar Galesong Pratama Manado. *Jurnal EMBA*, 2(1), 295-304
- [26.] Silaban, R. L., Handaru, A. W., & Saptono, A. (2021). Effect of Workload, Competency, and Career Development on Employee Performance with Organizational Commitment Intervening Variables. *The International Journal of Social Sciences World (TIJOSW)*, 3(01), 294–311. Retrieved from <https://www.growingscholar.org/journal/index.php/TIJOSW/article/view/126>
- [27.] Sundi, K. (2013). Effect of Transformational Leadership and Transactional Leadership on Employee Performance of Konawe Education Department at Southeast Sulawesi Province. *International Journal of Business and Management Invention*, 2(12), 50-58.
- [28.] Yarnall, Jane. 2011. Maximising The Effectiveness Of Talent Pools: A Review Of Case Study Literature. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 32(5):510-526.